

Ruminal Microbiome and Lipopolysaccharides

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Introduction

Bovine ruminal acidosis is a serious digestive tract disease caused by the use of highly fermentable feeds to boost productivity (Khafipour *et al.*, 2009). When a ruminant consumes large amounts of readily fermentable carbohydrates (RFCs) in a short period of time, or when the period of adaptation to RFCs is insufficient, RFCs are suddenly fermented and volatile fatty acids (VFAs) accumulate, causing the rumen pH to drop below 5.5 for an extended period of time and resulting in the condition of fermentative acidosis (Ding and Xu, 2003).

Lactic acid-producing bacteria, such as *Streptococcus bovis* and *Lactobacillus* spp., proliferate in this condition, resulting in an accumulation of lactic acid, which is known as lactic acidosis (Gozho *et al.*, 2007). It is a common gastrointestinal disorder that causes significant economic losses to the dairy industry due to a significant decrease in milk yield and a high mortality rate in acute cases (Patil *et al.*, 2008). Ruminants of all ages, breeds, and sexes are prone to grain and carbohydrate overeating (Radostitis *et al.*, 2007).

The resulting production of large amounts of volatile fatty acids (VFA) and lactic acid lowers rumen pH to non-physiological levels, weakening the rumen's buffering capacity and reducing the efficiency of rumen flora and fermentation. Ruminitis, metabolic acidosis, lameness, hepatic abscess, pneumonia, and death can all result from lactic acidosis.

Ruminal acidosis occurs when a large amount of highly fermentable carbohydrates, primarily starches and sugars, is consumed in a short period of time. This typically occurs when feedlot cattle are rapidly transitioned from roughage to high concentrate diets without proper adaptation, or when dairy cow intake during the pre- and post-partum transition is erratic (Beauchemin and Penner, 2009). It is also affected by the total load of readily fermentable

carbohydrates in the rumen, because dairy cows frequently experience subacute ruminal acidosis during peak carbohydrate consumption.

The clinical signs of acidosis vary according to the severity of the disease and can be acute, posing a life-threatening situation, or subacute (chronic), resulting in decreased feed consumption and weight gain. Repeated bouts of subacute ruminal acidosis can cause rumen wall surface damage. When the rumen wall is compromised, bacteria and toxins produced by bacteria can enter the portal circulation, resulting in liver abscesses and an inflammatory response (Gozho *et al.*, 2007). A variety of physiological effects may occur in acidotic animals, and the effects may be related to a variety of factors. Dry matter intake (DMI) is a clear cause of acidosis and has been used as a clinical sign to diagnose subacute ruminal acidosis.

As a result, the goal of this study is to explain how ruminal Gram-negative bacteria may contribute to the pathogenesis of ruminal acidosis by releasing lipopolysaccharides (LPS; a component of their cell wall) in the ruminal fluid. Normal fermentation is disrupted when cattle consume excessive amounts of highly fermentable carbohydrates without prior adaptation. Because of the accumulation of short-chain fatty acids and lactate in the rumen, the fermentation of these carbohydrates rapidly lowers ruminal pH. As a result, ruminal epithelium may be damaged and tissue function may be compromised, potentially leading to the translocation of pathogenic substances from the rumen into the bloodstream.

Such changes in fermentation are followed by an increase in Gram-positive bacteria and a decrease in Gram-negative bacteria. During ruminal acidosis, Gram-negative bacteria lyses increase the concentration of LPS in the rumen fluid. Because LPS is a highly proinflammatory endotoxin in the circulatory system, previous research has raised concerns about the role of ruminal LPS in the pathogenesis of ruminal acidosis. Although these disorders do not always result in an immune response in animals, recent research has shown that different Gram-negative bacteria have different LPS composition and toxicity, which may explain the differences in immune response. Given the diversity of Gram-negative bacteria in the rumen, examining changes in the bacterial community during ruminal acidosis could help identify which Gram-negative bacteria are linked to LPS release in the rumen. Nutritional strategies to overcome, or at least minimize, ruminal acidosis could be developed by identifying and targeting ruminal bacteria with potentially pathogenic LPS.

Gram-negative bacterial cell-wall structure with emphasis in the lipopolysaccharide (LPS) presence in the outer membrane. Toxicity is mainly associated with the lipid A composition. Courtesy of Yen-Ming Hsu, AB Biosciences, Inc. Boston, Massachusetts, USA.

The main factors to consider in preventing ruminal acidosis are carefully adapting the rumen to dietary changes, providing adequate Providing physically effective fiber (peNDF) concentration, and reducing the fermentability of the non-fiber carbohydrate fraction. Because a higher proportion of forage can be included in the diet without lowering its digestible energy content, the use of high-quality forages helps to mitigate the risk of ruminal acidosis.

Most diets are formulated for the average cow and do not include a margin of error to account for the variability among cows. As diets are formulated closer to the minimum level of peNDF and with higher concentrations of non-fiber carbohydrates, a greater portion of the cows will experience ruminal acidosis. Formulating diets for the average cow may be acceptable for cows in mid and late lactation, but diets for cows in early lactation need to account for the higher risk of these cows to experiencing acidosis.

References

- Khafipour, E., Plaizier, J.C. and Krause, D.C. 2009. Rumen microbiome composition determined using two nutritional models of sub-acute ruminal acidosis. *Appl. Env. Microbio.*, 75: 7115-7124.
- Ding, Z. and Xu, Y. 2003. Lactic acid is absorbed from the small intestine of sheep. *J. Exp. Zoo.*, 295(1): 29-36.
- Gozho, G.N., Plaizier J.C., Krause, D.O. 2007. Ruminal lipopolysaccharide concentration and inflammatory response during grain induced subacute ruminal acidosis in dairy cows. *J. Dairy Sc.*, 90: 856-866.

- Patil, N.A., Dhanapalan, P., Prathaban, S., Nambi, A.P. and Vijayarani, K. 2008. Therapeutic efficacy of *Megasphaera elsdeni* and *Veillonella parvula* in lactic acidosis. *Ind. J. Vet. Med.*, 28: 1-4.
- Radostitis, O.M., Gay, C.C., Hinchcliff, K.W. and Constable, P.D. 2007. Acute carbohydrate engorgement of ruminants. In: *Veterinary Medicine, a Text Book of the Disease of Cattle, Sheep, Pigs and Horses*, 10th edition, Elsevier publishing, pp. 314-325.
- Beauchemin, K. and Penner, G. 2009. New developments in understanding ruminal acidosis in dairy cows. *Tri-State Dairy Nutrition Conference*, 21-22 April, pp. 1-12.

